

ISic1657

I.Sicily inscription 1657

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble (red)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Crypt of S. Marziano

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 24397

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][u]is iam tricenos vitae
2. [complevera]t annos felix coniugium
3. [iamfecitillasuu]m da deus omnipotens
4. [coelestisglo]ria vitae digna cum
5. sanctis ut mereatur ibi
6. deposita est in pace d(o)m(in)i V nonas mart(ias)
7. post cons(ulatum) d(ominorum) n(ostrorum) Honorio XIII et Theodosio X
A(u)g(ustis)

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175844
EDR 072138
EDCS 12700079

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1906.0167

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio.*

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